

CHARACTERISTICS OF THE CLINICAL COURSE OF DEGENERATIVE SPINE INJURIES IN THE ELDERLY POPULATION.

Mirzajonov A.Sh.

Mamasoliev N.S.

Kalandarov D.M.

Usmanov B.U.

Andijan State Medical Institute Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10704408>

The purpose of the research is regional characteristics of the clinical course of degenerative spine injuries (DIS) in the elderly population in the conditions of Andijan.

Test material and methods. In 21 years of epidemiological monitoring, 2994 patients with degenerative spine injuries were comprehensively studied. < 20-year-olds - 25 (0.8%), 20-29-year-olds - 382 (12.8%), 30-39-year-olds - 511 (17.1%), 40-49-year-olds - 627 (20.9%), 50-59-year-olds - 721 (24.1%), 60-74-year-olds - 644 (21.5%) and ≥ 75 -year-olds - 84 (2.8%). Questionnaire, clinical instrumental and biochemical examination methods were used.

The average 21-year detection frequency of DIS does not differ significantly in the rural and urban population, with a prevalence of 70.1% and 71.2% [$\chi^2=0.353$; $C=0.011$; $RR=0.984$; 95% $CI=0.936-1.035$; $P>0.05$].

And, according to our analysis, a specific epidemiological trend is noticeable: until 2009, there was a decrease in DIS in rural conditions compared to urban conditions, and in the following years - it was observed that it "grew up to them".

The 21-year prevalence frequency of DIS is expressed by changes in the rural and urban population as follows: in 2000 - from 54.4% and 78.8% ($P<0.05$), in 2001 - from 83.3% and 62.4% ($P>0.05$), in 2002 - 88.6% and 100.0% ($P>0.05$), in 2003 - 59.3% and 100.0% ($P<0.001$), in 2004 - 73.2% and 100.0% ($P<0.05$), 2005 - 79.2% and 100.0% ($P<0.05$), 2006 - 65.7% and 100.0% ($P<0.05$), in 2007 - 83.3% and 100.0% ($P>0.05$), in 2008 - 60.0% and 100.0% ($P>0.05$), in 2009 - from 32.4% and 13.0% ($P>0.05$), in 2010 - from 38.7% and 29.4% ($P>0.05$), in 2011 - from 40.5% and from 63.0% ($P<0.05$), in 2012 - from 60.7% and 100.0% ($P<0.001$), in 2013 - from 52.7% and 54.1% ($P>0.05$), in 2014 - from 77.4% and 100.0% ($P<0.001$), in 2015 - from 74.9% and 90.0% ($P>0.05$), in 2016 - from 100.0% and 7.7% ($P<0.001$), 2017 - 100.0% and 15.2% ($P<0.001$), 2018 - 65.0% and 96.4% ($P<0.001$), in 2019 -

from 100.0% and 69.3% ($P < 0.001$) and in 2020 - from 95.8% and 100.0% ($P > 0.05$).

21-year DIS trend in the rural population - from 54.7% to 70.1% (with a difference of 15.4%) and in the urban population - from 78.8% to 100.0% (with a difference of 21.2%) is represented by

It is worth noting that DIS is detected in high frequencies and is represented by an increasing trend in recent years.

Characteristics of the prevalence of DIS in the population aged < 20 years and $\geq 20-75$ years depending on age were determined and evaluated.

The 21-year trend of DIS in different age groups. The frequency of DIS in the population of men and women is determined as follows: in < 20 years old - 30.8% and 58.3% ($P > 0.05$), in 20-29 years - 61.0% and from 56.7% ($P > 0.05$), at 30-39 - 70.0% and 72.3% ($P > 0.05$), at 40-49 - 69.8% and 71.2% ($P > 0.05$), at 50-59 - 69.0% and 72.3% ($P > 0.05$), at 60-74 - 75.4% and 75.3% ($P > 0.05$), and from ≥ 75 - 81.6% and 78.3% ($P > 0.05$).

Age-related frequency of detection of DIS in men is confirmed by 50.8% or 2.3-fold increase and in women - 20.0%, i.e. 1.3-fold increase [$\chi^2 = 1.075$; $C = 0.019$; $RR = 0.975$; 95% $CI = 0.930-1.022$; $P > 0.05$].

Obtained results and conclusions. In the years 2000-2020, the frequency of detection of traditional symptoms of DIS in the conditions of Andijan and among the population < 20 years old and $> 20-75$ years old is observed to be 26.3% on average, the frequency of its traditional appearance has increased by 4.9% ($\chi^2 = 0.517$; $C = 0.080$; $RR = 0.742$; 95% $CI = 0.324-1.699$; $P > 0.05$).

In the years 2000-2020, expression of pain in the hip joints increased from 23.1% to 26.8%, the frequency of expression of pain in passive flexion of the knee joint increased from 18.2% to 26.7%, and the frequency of joint pain in the paw joint increased from 25.0% and 23.1%. In the urban population, the frequency of detection of traditional clinical symptoms increased by 50% in 21 years [$\chi^2 = 2,357$; $S = 0.420$; $RR = 0.250$; 95% $CI = 0.017 - 3.624$; $P > 0.05$] and in the rural population, the frequency of such detection is confirmed not exceeding 7.0% [$\chi^2 = 0.009$; $S = 0.011$; $RR = 0.960$; 95% $CI = 0.404 - 2.280$; $P > 0.05$].

Implementation of the pharmacoepidemiological monitoring system in patients with degenerative spine damage eliminates side effects of treatment up to 85%. Provision of pharmacocontrol over 8 drugs (analgesics, nonsteroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs, chondroprotectors, sulfasalazine, immunodepressants, aminoquinolines and other drugs) and two surgical treatment methods (arthroplasty and special surgical procedures

THEORETICAL ASPECTS IN THE FORMATION OF PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

International scientific-online conference

performed on the spine, endoprosthesis procedure) modern pharmacotherapy secures programs and increases their efficiency.

